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ESTIMATION OF THE STANDARD VALUE OF IRRIGATED AGRICULTURAL LAND IN AKALTIN DISTRICT

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Abstract: This article shows that the evaluation of the normative value of irrigated agricultural land is always one of the most complex problems of the evaluation system. Because land areas are used for different purposes in the sectors of the economy, the issue of their evaluation requires a different approach. Therefore, the modern agricultural economy also creates the need to evaluate land plots in the same way as other means of production.

Keywords: agriculture, assessment, economy, soil, indicators, new, market relations, problems, law, horticulture.

Introduction: Normative assessment of land as the main means of agricultural production is of great importance. The successful solution of the evaluation problem requires, first of all, to correctly define its object and subject. One of the characteristics of the land as the main means of production in the rural economy is its productivity. According to a number of literatures on land [10,11,15,23], its ability to provide nutrients and moisture necessary for the good development of plants is called soil fertility. It is known that man affects the earth in various ways to increase soil fertility: he plows, softens, irrigates, fertilizes the soil, and so on. It increases the amount of nutrients in the soil and allows them to be easily assimilated by plants. Of course, there are a number of other measures that can increase soil fertility. But for positive changes in the quality of the soil of the plots of land used, additional funds and labor are required.

The study of existing scientific sources and practical developments shows that until today, a number of methodologies have been created for the normative assessment of agricultural land. In particular, of the last century

In the 1970s, the "All-Union Methodology of Normative Assessment of Lands" [16] was created, and based on this methodology, the lands of Uzbekistan intended for agricultural purposes were evaluated. According to the methodology,

according to the set goals and requirements, the normative assessment of land is divided into two parts: private and general:

1) Private assessment is aimed at determining the effectiveness of growing a certain agricultural crop under different soil conditions, and general assessment is aimed at determining the indicators describing the effectiveness of agricultural land use in the presence of an accelerated level of farming.

2) 2) In the general assessment of lands - the value of the gross product, reimbursement of costs, differentiated income; productivity, cost recovery, and differentiated income indicators are adopted in the private assessment. Evaluation indicators are highlighted in absolute (natural or grade) and relative value (points). They are usually calculated on the basis of the average level of acceleration of production.

Because of this, land valuation indicators have become outdated over time and, in this regard, require their updating every 5 years. In addition, it was not possible to carry out such work in these terms because the determination of evaluation indicators required the collection, processing, integration and analysis of large amounts of statistical data. During the years of independence, the positive changes that occurred in the agriculture of our country, in particular, the change in the forms of land use based on the land code, the transition to multi-unit farming, the transition to the use of land and other means of production on the basis of shares, required the creation of methodologies suitable for the new transitional conditions.

Such methodology was created by scientists of the "Market Reforms Scientific Research Institute" at the end of the last century [6]. The basis of this methodology is to determine the resource potential of agricultural land, and it is proposed to determine the economic value of land using the land evaluation indicators determined by the state scientific-project institute "Uzdaverloyiha" according to the previous economic evaluation methodology.

The development of market relations in the economic sectors of our republic, including agriculture, creates the need for a normative assessment of existing land areas, especially irrigated lands, from an economic point of view. The results of the normative assessment of agricultural land are mainly to determine the land tax rates, to build houses in rural areas and to grant land to farmers, to provide loans from banks, to determine the starting price for the sale of plots of land through auctions, and as provided by law. used for other cases.

53.59% of the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan is occupied by agricultural land, which is the main means of agricultural production. The distribution of land intended for agricultural purposes in the territory of the republic is determined according to natural climatic factors.

The Akaltin district, which is the object of our scientific research, is located in the south-western part of the Syrdarya region and was established on August 31, 1971. The district borders the Republic of Kazakhstan to the north, Mirzachol of Jizzakh region to the north-west, Dostlik districts to the south-west, Mirzaabad and Khavos districts to the north-east and south-east. The area is 551.0 km². There are 3 towns, 7 rural settlements and 13 mahallas in the territory of the district. Center of Sardoba town. The terrain is mainly flat and consists of the Mirzachol plain. The soils are different. In some farms, underground water has surfaced, and in these areas, salty soils are scattered. Open and closed collectors have been built against salinity. The lands are irrigated from the South Mirzachol Canal and the Central Branch Canal.

General information of Akaltin district of Syrdarya region

It is given in table 1.

Table 1

GENERAL INFORMATION

REGION	SIRDARYA
DISTRICT	AKALTIN
CENTER	<i>SARDOBA TOWN</i>
TIME OF FORMATION	<i>31.08.1971</i>
TOTAL AREA km²	<i>551,0 km²</i>
SITIES SUBORDINATE TO THE DISTRICT	-
THE NUMBER OF ASSEMBLIES OF RURAL CITIZENS	-
NUBER OF COMMUNITY GATHERINGS	<i>13</i>
RURAL SETTLEMENTS	<i>7</i>
THE PERMANENT POPULATION AS OF APRIL1,2024. THOUSAND PEOPLE	<i>56,0</i>
<i>м.жс.:MEN</i>	<i>28,2</i>
WOMEN	<i>27,8</i>
DISTANCE TO REGIONAL CENTERS,km	<i>45</i>
BORDER REPUBLIC	<i>Kazakistan republic,Jizzakh region</i>
BORDER DISTRICT	<i>Mirzachol, Dostlik, Mirzabad, Khavos.</i>

The distribution of the volume of production of agricultural products by categories of farms in January-March 2024, the volume of production of agricultural products by all categories of farms is 139.1 bln. soum or the growth rate compared to the corresponding period of 2023 was 102.6 percent.

Using the above methodology, in the example of the "Sabox" farm engaged in cotton cultivation in the Usman Nasir region of the Akaltin district of the Syrdarya region, 1 hectare. we determine the standard value of the area occupied by cotton. The cotton area is 50 hectares, the bonnitet score of the plot is 60, the calculated amount of agricultural production profit is 18%, the capitalization percentage of the calculated profit is 5.

So, to 1hectare.The standard productivity of the cotton crop is determined by the following formula:

$$MUp = MHp * XBp = 0,4 \text{ c/he} * 60 \text{ ball bonitet point} * 88 \text{ thousand soums} = 2112 \text{ thousand soums.}$$

1 hectare. We determine the calculated profit from the cotton field:

$$HChF = \frac{M * Up * PM}{100} * HSchMD = \frac{2112 * 50}{100} * 18 = \frac{1,056 * 18}{50} = \frac{19008}{50} = 38016$$

After that, 1 hectare. We determine the standard value of the cotton area

$$MQp = \frac{HChF * K_1 * K_2 * K_3}{\Phi} * 100 = \frac{38016 * 1,2 * 0,950 * 0,967}{5} * 100 = \frac{41908,1}{5} * 100 = 838162 \text{ soums}$$

So 1 hectare. The standard value of the field is 838162 soums.

The standard value of the total cotton area is equal to (50 * 838162) 41908100 soums.

Farm 50 hectares. A single land tax of {(41908100*6)/100} 2514486 soums is paid for the land in one year.

Table 1 shows the standard value of agricultural land of agricultural producers in Okoltin district of Syrdarya region.

Table 1. Estimated standard price of agricultural goods producers of Okoltin district

T/p	The name of the producers of agricultural goods	Speciality	Areas of main agricultural crops in irrigated arable land, hectare					Average credit rating of irrigated land	percentage of areas where the use of toxic chemicals is restricted %	The coefficient that takes into account the method of water release for irrigation	total	
			Cotton	Grain with spikes	Vegetables	Alfalfa of previous years	Other plants				Field, km	Total price, thousand soums
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1	‘‘AJOYIB DALA SAHOVATI’’	Horticulture-viticulture			6,4		1,2	50	1	1	10,4	259990,2
2	‘‘TOIROVDAGI BOG‘I’’	Horticulture-viticulture			4,9		3	46	1	1	8	164186,0
3	‘‘SIRLI OQ QUSHLAR’’	Others					2,6	40	1	1	4,7	25398,6
4	‘‘HAZRATI AKMAL QURBON’’	Others						47	1	1	85,41	1366335,1
5	‘‘OQOLTIN AGRO PILLA’’	Others						49	1	1	20,18	215023,7
6	‘‘MIRZABOD SARDOBA HAMKOR’’MCHJ	Others						46	1	1	22,9	249162,5
7	‘‘SHODLIKDAGI BAXTIYOR BOG‘BON’’ f/x	Horticulture-viticulture							1	0,88	10	2148,8
8	‘‘SHERZOD XURSHID CHORVADOR’’	Animal husbandry					13,2	43	1	1	13,2	64422,1
9	‘‘BAXODIR-UCHQUN FAYZ’’ f/x	Others						50	1	1	14,4	16741,9
10	‘‘INDORAMA AGRO’’ MCHJ XK	Cotton-grain farming	361,8	500				47	1	1	1134,61	12288780,8

11	"OLTIN QO`L FAYZLI BALIG`I"	Others						49	1	1	29,7	33839,6
12	"BAXODIR-NURIDDIN-KOMILJON ‘”	Others						50	1	1	26,8	512754,5
13	"QO`YCHILIK PAXLAVONLARI”	Others						48	1	1	18,1	20201,9
14	"JASURBEK FAYZ SAVDO” MCHJ	Others						55	1	1	49,32	87662,5
15	"FISH HAUS GRAND” MCHJ	Others						46	1	1	118,9	589254,6
16	"XUSAN AZIZ NURIDD ‘”	Horticulture-viticulturek				5		47	1	1	5	74916,4
17	"OQOLTIN SABZAVOTI”	Vegetable farming			5,4			50	1	1	4,3	119702,3
18	"CHORVA TOMORQA TA`MINOTI" MCHJ	Othersr						43	1	1	69,5	154079,0
19	"SHODLIKDAGI BOG`BONLAR”	Horticulture-viticulture			5,8		1	50	1	1	5,7	143594,9
20	"ASADBEK ALISHER RASHID CHORVASI"	Animal husbandry				10,5		47	1	1	14	123677,4
21	"TILLA BALIQ BARAKASI”	Others						50	1	1	10,21	11870,5
22	"BARAKA JALOL HAMKOR”	Others				7,5	9,7	48,5	1	1	27,34	296431,1
23	"AMUR FISH" MCHJ	Others						45	1	1	64,6	199798,1
24	"OQOLTIN SARDOBA BALIG`I” MCHJ	Others						45	1	1	221,7	1819360,6
25	"SARDOBA TEMIR YO`L AGROSANOAT MAJMUASI ” MCHJ	Others						48	1	1	396,3	3994960,6
26	"AOLTIN AGRO PILLA” MCHJ	Others						57	1	1	11,49	90663,5
27	"TEMUR SHUXRAT BIRLIGI” φ/x	Others						55	1	1	13,4	68333,6
28	"OZODBEK OYBEK ORZUSI” φ/x	Catton-grain farming	34,6	40	3			52	1	1	80,3	1474322,3
29	"OZODBEK DOSTON	Others						55	1	1	47,77	909275,2

	BOBOBEK"											
30	"XOJIAKBAR-SHERZOD-OZODBEK"	Others						52,5	1	1	45,2	821249,6
	TOTAL											26198138

Figure 1 shows the distribution of agricultural products produced in January-March 2024 by categories of farms.

Fig. 1. Distribution of agricultural products of Akaltin district by categories of farms

As of April 1, 2024, there are 3,792 head of large horned cattle, including 1,420 head of cows, 8,374 head of sheep and goats, 274 head of horses, 17,798 head of poultry.

Land resources in Akaltin district are mainly used for the following purposes.

Vegetable farming

Policemanship–1500 hectares.

Gardening–2000 hectares .

Animal husbandry–2000 hectares .

Birding–100 hectares .

Fishing–100 hectares .

Other directions–346 hectares .

Poteto planting plan –574 hectares .

Vegetable planting plan–323 hectares .

Soybean planting plane–600 hectares .

Raspberry planting plan –300 000 pieces

Tree planting plan for green space –2 000 000 pieces

When it comes to assessing the value of agricultural land, it is very important to calculate its true value. Of course, this issue is one of the important problems facing agricultural science in today's market conditions. Persons who treat the land, especially agricultural land, in an unfriendly manner, damage agricultural land, pollute it with various wastes and harmful substances, and do not take timely measures against salinity and erosion should be held accountable. This is reflected in the current normative documents. But in order to quantitatively measure exactly such cases, it is required to estimate the actual normative value of such lands.

From the above, it can be concluded that a great amount of scientific and practical work has been done on the assessment of agricultural land in the past, the results of which are successfully used today. But the developing market economy creates the need to assess the real value of agricultural land. Creating and implementing such a methodology will be an important factor in positively solving the above problems.

USED LITERATURE

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, Adolat, 2023.
2. Land Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, Adolat, 1998.
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. “On the State Land Cadastre”. Tashkent., Adolat, 1998

4. 4. National Report of the Cadastre Agency under the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2024.
5. 5. Provisional method for determining the qualitative, economic and value assessment of agricultural land in the Republic of Uzbekistan. T., “Uzdavyerloyikha” State Scientific-Design Institute 1998.
6. 6. Abdullaev Z.S. Modeling the processes of assessing the value of land resources. T. Publishing House of the National Library of Uzbekistan named after Alisher Navoi, 2013.
7. 7. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5742 dated June 17, 2019 “On measures for the effective use of land and water resources in agriculture”.
8. 8. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 235 dated August 18, 2014 “On improving the system for determining the normative value of agricultural arable land” (Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2014).
9. 9. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UF-5853 dated October 23, 2019 “On approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030”.
10. 10. S.A. Avezbayev, S.N. Volkov. Land development design. Tashkent, New Century Generation, 2004.
11. 11. S.A. Avezbayev, S.N. Volkov. Scientific foundations of land formation. Tashkent, New Age Generation, 2004.
12. 12. S.A. Avezbayev, T.M. Karabayeva. Land formation. Tashkent, 2005.
13. 13. Turayev R.A. Improving the methodology for monitoring irrigated lands. Doctor of Science (DSc.) dissertation. Abstract. Tashkent, 2021.
14. 14. Turayev R.A., Davronov O.U., Sharopov R.N. Monitoring in pastures and pastures. Scientific and methodological manual Tashkent: “Fan ziyosi” publishing house, 2021.
15. 15. All-Union methodology for economic assessment of lands (temporary). Mytishi, GIZR, 1976.
16. 16. Bobojonov A.R., Rahmonov Q.R., Gafirov A.J. “Land Cadastre”. T.: Cholpon, 2002
17. 17. Babajanov A.R., Kamalova D. M., Roziboev S.B. Land cadastre. Textbook, part 2. T., TAQI, 2016
18. 18. Babajanov A.R., Roziboev S.B. Cadastre of residential areas. T., Tafakkur, 2011
19. 19. Babajanov A.R., Nishonov A.M., Nazarov B.R. Fundamentals of real estate state cadastre. T., Period, 2012

20. 20. Uzbekistan in numbers. Statistical collection. T., Economy and finance, 2017.

21. 21. Ruziboyev S.B. Optimization of land and crop types in the organization of land use (on the example of Kashkadarya region). Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences.

22. Textbook Land cadastre A.R. Bobojonov, D.M. Kamalova, S.B. Roziboyev

22. 23. Babadzhanov A.R., Roziboev S.B. Prospects for dry land use. Agroilm, 2020, No. 5.

23. 24. Information of the statistics department of Akaltin district.

24. 25. Passport of Akaltin district.

25. www.lex.uz